

CONFLICTS OF IDENTITY IN KILEY REID'S *SUCH A FUN AGE***DR. DEBJANI DUTTA**Independent Researcher
BA, MA (Jadavpur University)
& PhD (EFLU) in English Literature**ABSTRACT**

*In Kiley Reid's novel *Such A Fun Age* (2019) questions of race, identity and privilege take centre-stage as the life of its protagonist Emira Tucker unravels on the side. Both casual and ingrained racism come to the fore in incidents layered to reveal the canker at the heart of modern-day American society. Drawing on bell hooks' project of critiquing the institutional prejudice which ties race to capital and class, this paper will look at how Reid's novel illuminates the anxieties that haunt the life of a young black woman surrounded by problematizing polarities of white fragile selves who make a pretence at mere verbal solidarity. It will attempt to understand the ramifications which attach to each character in Reid's text as the boundaries of working-class reality clashes with the enforcement of white supremacy thinly veiled as 'fragility,' in the process upending lives and restructuring identities.*

Keywords: Race, Class, Identity, White Fragility, White Privilege, Discrimination, Activism, Antagonism.

1. Introduction

Kiley Reid's 2019 novel *Such A Fun Age* is a meditation on various issues that are of topical interest in the United States of the present day, chief amongst them issues of race, class, and privilege. The narrative deals with the story of a twenty-five-year-old Black woman by the name of Emira Tucker and the way her life is affected by the turn of events that follow in the steps of her employment by an upper middle class white woman, Alix Chamberlain. Emira is busy attending the birthday party of one of her closest friends when a late-night call from her employer, Mrs. Chamberlain, disrupts her neatly laid plans. She is asked, at short and urgent notice, whether she would be willing to pick up her charge Briar (the three-year-old child who Emira babysits) and take her to the local grocery store while Mrs. Chamberlain clears up some mess with the police. There are two hooks in the easy presentation of this scene by the author, and both have to do with monetary situations. I'd argue that Emira is not so much asked as 'tasked' with this job, outside of her work hours, by Mrs. Chamberlain promising to pay her double her usual amount. The prospect of extra cash makes Emira dwell on the state of her current financials – "a total of seventy-nine dollars and sixteen cents ... Emira Tucker could really use the cash." (Reid, 2019, p. 9). What follows after Emira accepts the job is not something anyone could have anticipated, but it is the one issue that lies at the crux of this novel.

While at the local grocery store (Market Depot), Emira is accused of kidnapping the white child in her charge by the security guard, who is in turn alerted to this possible (but preposterous) "crime" (Reid, 2019, p. 24) by an apparently well-meaning white woman. The latter had overheard little Briar saying that she wasn't with her own mother and had dropped to the conclusion that she might have been held against her wishes, even when the

circumstances surrounding the confrontation with the guard spelled anything but danger. Emira is understandably upset over what she believes is a completely unnecessary altercation – “All at once, on top of the surreptitious accusations, this entire interaction seemed completely humiliating, as if she’d been loudly told that her name was not on a guest list.” (Reid, 2019, p. 21) – and she feels doubly hedged in when, after having to explain herself and give reasons as to why she might be hanging out late at night with a little kid, she realizes that the entire incident is being video-taped by another customer, unsurprisingly another white man. Emira tries in vain to give reasons explaining her position vis-à-vis her young charge – “I’m her sitter. I’m technically her nanny...” (Reid, 2019, p. 21), but it is not till she is forced to make a phone call to the father of the child that things start to solve themselves. The fact that Emira has to resort to the dependency of a white male to come to her rescue (despite the fact that the white male in question is the child’s father Peter Chamberlain, the only authority who could possibly back up her claims) is not lost on the discerning reader – the role of a white saviour turning up to save the protagonist is a long shadow that will cast itself over the rest of the text. For it is not just Peter but also the figure of Kelley Copeland – the person who is busy videotaping the entire grocery store incident – who has a large part to play in the events of Emira’s life.

Kelley is another white person who (initially) disregards Emira’s words – she asks him to stop filming the scene but all Kelley seems keyed to is the litigious power of the video grab. Kelley’s subject position, as one who feels himself keenly attuned to the lived experiences of people of colour (in this instance, Black), is one which brings to mind the arguments of Robin DiAngelo regarding the opinion of white people about issues of race. DiAngelo, in her book titled *White Fragility* (2018), states that in a society where race is a very brick of the societal building order, it is often difficult to encounter a person of white heritage who does not have a voluble opinion on racism. White people’s opinions on race – “arguably the most complex and enduring social dynamic of the last several hundred years” (DiAngelo, 2018, p. 28) – is one which is often misinformed and bereft of any clear idea as to how to “engage critically with the topic of race.” (DiAngelo, 2018, p. 28). The character of Kelley, as we will see, harkens to that understanding of a white person who has a very unfortunate binary in how to deal with questions of race – that a person who commits an act of discrimination based on race is one who is morally suspect. This understanding of a morally suspect individual is one which Kelley associates not only with the guard who accosts Emira, who is in actuality a peripheral character, but more tellingly with the person of Alix Chamberlain, the other powerful persona in this novel who is responsible for the churn of events that threaten to engulf Emira’s life.

It is Alix’s (boundary-breaching, privacy-invading) phone call which starts the novel rolling. It is the process through which she tries to manipulate her position of power (as the employer of Emira) that thoroughly reveals her motives regarding her own affluence and her very problematic views on what consists possible iterations of politically correct behaviour, that helps Reid form her novel of satire about the very inherent prejudices of white folks. Alix is another of the white saviour figures who think it is their duty to somehow compensate for their wealth and lifestyle by trying to ‘identify’ with people of a different social, cultural, and economic background – here embodied by her employee Emira Tucker. In trying to read the character of Alix Chamberlain, I will borrow from bell hooks’ arguments about the nature and complexity of rich white people who fail to come to terms with the nexus of their privilege, class, economic wealth, and social currency, written about in *Where We Stand*

(2000). Alix is the very epitome of the consumerist class and its “notion of individualism that seduces everyone, the haves and have-nots alike.” (hooks, 2000, p. 72), who mistakenly (prejudicially) confuses her letter-writing transactions (on the back of which she has built a successful career) with having a transactional relationship with her babysitter, Emira. This paper will try to parse *Such A Fun Age* by examining, in subsequent sections, the relationships which form the story’s core – a) that of Emira with Alix, b) between Emira and Kelley, and c) the coterminous early history betwixt Alix and Kelley (which I’d argue inform both their adult personhoods), before concluding with a deliberation on how these criss-crossing lives form the moment of tension which Kiley Reid offers up for her readers’ reflection.

2. Self and the other: Alix and Emira

In her book *Uneasy Street* (2017), a study of the anxieties connected with the material culture of the wealthy, Rachel Sherman talks at length about the way the wealthy and the affluent approach their lifestyles. She argues that these people are aware of the growing inequality of the culture and the times they inhabit, and have found ways to navigate the extent of their privilege. In her study spanning a range of households and income thresholds, Sherman (2017) found that many of her participants were rather uncomfortable about openly discussing their financial worth and material assets. Talking about money was a deeply private detail and the circle of people with whom such conversations carried out similarly restricted. “When we talked outside, they kept their voices down so their neighbors wouldn’t hear; inside, some closed the door when the nanny was in the next room.” (Sherman, 2017, p. 18). This sense of something being amiss about the vast amounts of wealth an individual or a family possesses is something we can find in Reid’s text. The sense of privilege and safety that comes with wealth and class is evident in the way the Chamberlains lead their lives, but never more so than in the way Alix Chamberlain behaves around Emira. On hearing of the incident at the grocery store, Alix admits to “freaking out” (Reid, 2019, p. 63). Her reaction to the incident is to blame herself for not somehow being able to normalize her babysitter’s situation, or not paying her the attention she had deserved – “Most days, Alix practically threw Briar into Emira’s arms on her way out the door... she had no idea if her babysitter was the type of person to cry, sue, or do nothing at all.” (Reid, 2019, p. 63). According to bell hooks, “consumer culture and consumerism are woven through a notion of individualism that seduces everyone, the haves and have-nots alike.” (hooks, 2000, p. 72). Consumer culture is at the heart of Alix’s labour and she is acutely concerned about the kind of backlash she might have to face as a result of being associated with an incident of such inimical discrimination. It can be argued that more than really caring for Emira’s mental health vis-à-vis the incident, Alix likes the thought of herself being so worked up about her Black babysitter’s situation. She undertakes a conference call with her circle of friends (Rachel, Tamara, Jodi) to try to come to terms with the situation. Alix tries her utmost to get a reading of how the incident may have affected Emira’s life, but there is a personal stake in the sudden vociferous interest too. She is concerned about losing Emira (should Emira decide to give up her job and distance herself from the employers to whom the occurrence of events could indirectly be chalked up) and how that might impact Alix’s project of writing a book – “I’ll never be able to finish this book without her.” (Reid, 2019, p. 64). Thus starts Alix’s second project – that of trying to overcompensate for selfishly disregarding the existence of her babysitter. But this overcompensation was never required in the first place, and by the end of the novel readers understand how much of an imposition it is on Emira.

To try and understand why Alix tries to become more of a friend than an employer to Emira (this subject positioning is entirely through the perspective of Alix, who chooses to stay ignorant of her position of power over Emira), perhaps we might look at the reasons which made Alix shift residences from New York to Philadelphia. Alix had a burgeoning career in NY, a successful marriage, and a child who she could take care of herself, with only the intervention of her friends on a kind of need-to basis. It is the news of a second pregnancy and the concomitant space constraints which it puts on her and her husband Peter that is the reason for their joint decision to remove to Philadelphia, where “a ticket to a movie wasn’t fourteen dollars, it was ten” (Reid, 2019, p. 45) and she could exchange her apartment for a brownstone. Since most of her work could be accomplished just as well from within her home, the Chamberlains completed the move, although it didn’t entirely leave Alix satisfied. The incident with Emira gives Alix a chance at some kind of cause – in this case trying to objectify her Black domestic worker in order to try and get to comprehend her personhood better. It is what I would call an elaborate ruse, and it all unravels by the time we get to the end of the story. bell hooks, quite like Sherman, is unstinting in her view that talking or displaying wealth in an increasingly consumerist society is more often taboo than not. Displaying greed can come off as against the myth promoted and circulated by the media of a “classless society” (hooks, 2000, p. 71), all in their pursuit of fetching the American dream. There is a kind of greed in the nature of Alix’s trying to monopolize Emira’s time and personal space. She singles out her babysitter and offers to lend an ear or a helpful hand if Emira ever needs to unburden. She tries to singularly signify an incident that Emira would much prefer to forget (given Emira’s unwillingness to either pursue action against the guard or try and get herself any footage in the media about her harrowing experience) by constantly trying to start interpersonal conversations, with questions ranging from what subject Emira majored in to what allergies she might have (Reid, 2019, p. 82). She also purposely gives Emira monetary compensation (“an envelope with six hundred seventy-two dollars”), in the belief that it is not something she would be able (or willing) to turn down, even when Emira doesn’t warm to the myriad questions asked of her, or encourage the sudden interest being taken in her life.

Emira herself was brought up in a family that believed in fending for yourself from a very early age. Her father is a bee-store owner and her mother a book binder, and the emphasis is on work is worship, especially when worked with their own hands (Reid, 2019, p. 54). Majoring in English from Temple University, Emira is quite adept at transcription and typing (125 words per minute) and holds a second job with the Green Party as transcriptionist. When bell hooks (2000) talks about how the vast majority of the affluent take pains to keep the knowledge of their economy-handling skills private, it is a comment on how the wealthy strengthen the investment in consumption culture. Some of the working class, certainly those without the privileges that attach, are led into thinking that an identification (or a need to replicate, when possible) with the consumer lifestyle of the rich can lead to an assumption of equal standing. However, this is a seduction which Emira easily sidesteps – we see often that she refuses to take a taxi even when she’s paid for the ride, preferring rather to save the money for some future need, as also when she refuses any extra money for the pair of shorts she buys for Briar (Reid, 2019, p. 116). She is also acutely aware of the privilege syndrome which Alix so unsuccessfully tries to shake off – “Mrs. Chamberlain had expensive tastes that she never openly acknowledged... Emira couldn’t help but wonder why Mrs. Chamberlain couldn’t feel good paying full price for things when she could obviously afford it.” (Reid, 2019, p. 116). In this manner it is the masking of class privilege which hooks (2000) alludes

to when she talks about the fears of the rich– that they might believe their attraction is tied to their material worth, and so they try and play down their needs and desires. Emira however is very susceptible to what may be defined as the limited boundaries of her class and social status. She is volubly anxious about the expiry of her family health plan, the diminishing returns of a babysitting job which doesn't allow for the full existence of benefits, going so far as to hold herself responsible for the incident at the store “wouldn't have happened if you had a real fucking job” (Reid, 2019, p. 59). Her anxiety about acquiring a nine-to-five normal job is so palpable that she also suffers from a sense of not belonging in the same social strata as her clique of friends (Reid has equally balanced Alix and Emira with three close friends each). While her friend Shaunie is well-off, another friend Josefa is self-sufficient while pursuing a second Master's degree and working as a research fellow at Drexel (Reid, 2019). It is Zara with whom Emira bonds best, perhaps due to a shared working-class background. Emira's perception of the goals of adulthood are similarly influenced by her circle of friends and the influence they each wield in their separate professional domains. The fact that such a domain has so far eluded Emira is something which is a painful fact for her to digest, served up in the constant reminders she puts to herself about finding a new job, something more permanent and with benefits.

While discussing the privilege wielded by certain black people, bell hooks (2000) talks about the pressure to assimilate into “mainstream white culture to increase their class and power” (p. 92). While certain of the community continue to work for the upliftment of the entire group, some are only bent on exploitation for their personal gains. Those fixated on flexing their power and status undermine the nature of community bonds, believing rather in the maxim of “every woman and man “live for yoself, for yoself and nobody else.”” (hooks, 2000, p. 93). The representation of blackness today, as hooks (2000) clarifies, is predominantly led by those black people who find themselves aligned on the side of the materially advantaged. “these conservative black elites, chosen and appointed to positions of authority by the mainstream” (hooks, 2000, p. 95) take it upon themselves to redirect the course of underprivileged fellows, by pointing out to them the right or wrong of way. Such a figure can be delineated in Alix's friend Tamara, who unduly tries to influence Emira into her own way of seeing, interpreting, and navigating the world. At the Thanksgiving dinner (where Kelley and Alix's paths converge for the second time), Tamara decides to instruct Emira on the way to wear her braids or how she should go about applying for graduate school (“What was your GPA at Temple?”) (Reid, 2019, p. 228). But once again, Emira displays her resourcefulness when she picks up that Tamara is playing a role assigned to her (perhaps at Alix's behest) of trying to get into her good books by affecting an interest in her personal life. The tried and tested ruse of another guest “foisted on her by a well-meaning but ignorant host” (Reid, 2019, p. 214) is a bluff that Emira well comprehends, but like other things in her life, is unwilling to confront head-on. These are just some of the verbal and cerebral jousts which Alix and Emira exchange before the night of the Thanksgiving party, when, unknowing to both of them, the third admixture of Kelley Copeland plays his intrinsic part in the shake-up of the normative order ensuing until that moment.

3. The misplaced activism of Kelley Copeland

The character of Kelley Copeland first makes his entry by way of being a white saviour – in spite of being asked to not videotape the incident at the grocery store, he announces his arrival in the text by going viscerally against the grain of Emira's request. In fact, he shows his keenness in trying to persuade Emira, a person he's just met, into taking some kind of

action against the guard, either to ensure she gets some coverage in the media via a write-up or at least the cushion of “free groceries for a year.” (Reid, 2019, p. 28). Kelley is that example of white fragility who prefers to unsettle unexamined assumptions (DiAngelo, 2018), by visiting them in binaries. It is difficult for Kelley, chained in by notions of his own individualism as he is, to understand the kind of negative backlash Emira might face were she to pursue a case against the guard, or even worse, the kind of public scrutiny she would come under if the video were to air. DiAngelo argues that in the construction of white fragility, individualism, and objectivity both have an equal part to play. “Objectivity tells us that it is possible to be free of all bias.” (DiAngelo, 2018, p. 29) – it is this keen belief in his own outlook which informs Kelley every step of the way. There are several examples in the text, in the brief relationship that forms between Emira and Kelley, which reinforces the notion of Kelley’s being unable to acknowledge his own subjectivity as lying outside of the constraints of everyday racism.

As Emira gets to know Kelley better, she becomes aware of how comfortable Kelley seems to think he is when talking about black people, going so far as to use the racially charged N-word in casual conversation with Emira. Even when Emira observes to herself that Kelley doesn’t match the spectrum of other white men that she has dated (who condescendingly and out of a need to appear politically/socially aware start talking about minimum wage and MLK), she would still have preferred if he could have been more sensitive of the reaction of others before committing himself so adamantly into seeming familiar with black people and their lived experiences. While Kelley might have a tin ear when it comes to detecting his own discrimination, it does not excuse the fact of his prejudicial awareness of somehow being allowed to get away with using a pejorative roundly considered offensive by that very group of people who he would fain identify/walk shoulder-to-shoulder with. “...if what we feel is more subtle, such as mild discomfort, the discrimination is likely to also be subtle, even hard to detect.” (DiAngelo, 2018, p. 38). Kelley is overtly confident in the way he believes he can navigate through Black culture – sample his comment about he has “the music tastes of a middle-aged black woman,” (Reid, 2019, p. 99). Emira hesitates to point out how this deliberately invokes suggestions of fetishism, something her friend Josefa is the first to point out to her. Another example of Kelley being tone deaf (while appearing to be all-meaning) is when he refers to himself as also belonging to the working-class. When Emira brings a bottle of Riesling (given her as another token of compensation by Alix) to a date, Kelley purports to not be able to afford that family of wine, but it is a carefully constructed semantic which Emira can see through. “This was another thing that she’d decided she would let Kelley get away with: considering himself working class.” (Reid, 2019, p. 118). Kelley’s entire act of activism borders on co-opting roles, whereby he could somehow feel worked up to argue for the rights of people of color. He is blissfully unaware of his own privilege when he shares the history of his own past experience with Alix, roundly putting Emira’s boss to blame for participating and enabling racial bias – “Alix completely gets off on either having black people working for her or calling the cops on them...” (Reid, 2019, p. 243). The irony of one white male (Kelley) having cast another white female (Alix) in the constructed binaries of positive/negative is not lost on the discerning reader. Kelley believes he has an open mind, is well-intentioned and progressive, while Alix is the very epitome of the opposites – bigoted, prejudiced, and ignorant of producing the very racism she professes to so abhor. Again, it is easy for Emira to gauge the extent of Kelley’s fervid rant – he will never comprehend the reality of Emira’s situation, that “if she weren’t working for *this* Mrs. Chamberlain, she’d probably be working

for another one.” (Reid, 2019, p. 242, emphasis original). Kelley’s consumption of Black culture therefore comes across as mere lip-service, as something that probably embodies the germs of liberal values but which are hollow from the inside given his native inability to understand just how embedded his own politics are in a “false dichotomy” of the good/bad frame (DiAngelo, 2018). However, it is when Emira is caught in the crossfire between the destabilizing zones of Alix and Kelley’s history, following Thanksgiving dinner, that we hear more of the obsessive fetishist tendencies of both Kelley Copeland and Alex Murphy.

4. Conclusion: Histories of antagonism and their parlous effects

At the Thanksgiving dinner, a story within Reid’s overarching story is introduced. It is almost like a separate item on the menu, however one that was not within the knowledge of either of its two main participants. The two actors of this single (or singular) chapter from history are Alix and Kelley, unlikely compatriots who both play a role in Emira’s life up to this point. It so happened that both Emira’s employer and boyfriend were acquainted with each other and they both shared a fractious history. This history can be traced to their high school sojourn, when Alix (then Alex Murphy) was dating Kelley Copeland. Alix’s family came into a fortune on the death of her grandparents and a subsequent legal wrangle brought a huge sum of damages to her parents which enabled them to move precariously up the ladder of affluence, to the point where they had all the wealth they could dream of and could afford a type of “textbook McMansion” (Reid, 2019, p. 135). Clearly part of the *nouveau riche*, Alix (in sections that focalize her side of the story) narrates the incident that scarred her senior year to her eager friends. The Murphy family “purchased the services of Mrs. Claudette Laurens...a light-skinned black woman with curly gray hair” (Reid, 2019, p. 136) who kept house and hearth for the family. Alix quickly mashes over the details of how the housekeeper had to wear a uniform to reveal that Kelley broke her trust and invited a gang of boys in to her house to raise mayhem while her parents were away. It is Alix’s firm belief (even though she later found evidence to the contrary) that Kelley breached the secret of a private letter between the two of them to a popular Black boy from high school – Robbie Cormier, just so that Kelley could appear cool in the company of the high school topper. The breach of her family boundaries forced Alix to call the police, Cormier was arrested and stripped of a scholarship, and Alix became the butt of ridicule, sarcasm, and mockery at every turn in school. It turned out that her family property used to house a plantation and the severe criticism aimed at Alix for calling the police on a black boy at her home was enough to drive a permanent wedge between the budding love between herself and Kelley. Alix is referred to as “Massa Murphy” (Reid, 2019, p. 146) – obvious epithets recalling a slave-owning past, and it is this slight that she can never live down and what actually informs her conduct later in adult life. The unhealthy cathexis that readers have seen her develop for Emira’s personal space – invading the privacy of her cell phone, asking pointed questions about her life decisions, encouraging her to use the Chamberlain family computer on the off chance that she forgets to logout (which eventually Emira does) – we see in all of these actions the “defensiveness of [the] white fragility” (DiAngelo, 2018, p. 33) that is constantly at play within Alix’s personhood. Her past actions lead her to resist interrogating her present dilemmas, a kind of psychological barrier which blinds her to her prejudice – the judgemental outlook she holds about Emira. Alix is surprised that someone who listens to “songs with titles like “Dope Bitch” and “Y’all Already Know”” (Reid, 2019, p. 107) could also be aware of (in her opinion) high-falutin words like “connoisseur”. It is also perfectly cringeworthy

when we see Alix wondering how an aesthetically pleasing aquarium could occupy the same linear space as the rest of Emira’s humble apartment (Reid, 2019, p. 329).

Kelley is someone who will not admit his white privilege, who will perforce deny having any such, but it is his willingness to play saviour which marks him out as one who fails to admit the network of actions which visibly advantage whites against peoples of color. In his past history, Kelley jumped at the chance to side with his high-school’s most popular boy, a boy who also happened to be Black. By deciding to go to the rescue of Robbie Cormier following the incident of the police being called on him while at Alix’s mansion, Kelley displays his disconcerting need to play protector. It is this role which substantiates his own selfhood for him, as always coming out on all the right sides of binaries. The bias of racism is largely unconscious, argues DiAngelo (2018), which is how it meets its biggest challenge – defensiveness. “This defensiveness is classic white fragility because it protects our racial bias while simultaneously affirming our identities as open-minded.” (DiAngelo, 2018, p. 58) – Kelley falls prey to this very pronouncement, when after standing by Cormier and feasting on the optics of the situation, he later turns to an absolute vilification of Alex Murphy. He not only distances himself from her, he also pointedly starts dating a “light-skinned black girl with braids” (Reid, 2019, p. 149). Kelley blames Alix for the entire episode and cautions Emira to leave her employer. But in trying to advise Emira just because he dates her and therefore understands her concerns, Kelley runs the error of infantilizing a Black person’s subjectivity into something that can be easily regurgitated. We understand that neither Alix nor Kelley have been able to live down the discord and resentment of their high school days, and it is by making Emira a pawn in their battle for comeuppance as the saviour-hero that both run aground of our protagonist.

Alix’s voyeuristic appetite leads her to leak the video of the grocery store incident, in the hopes of milking the resulting outrage to her own benefit. Not only does she cause pernicious harm to the cause of Emira her babysitter, who has all along faithfully taken care of Briar (while Alix herself has failed or given up as a parent), she makes a final gambit of offering Emira a way out of her predicament. She has been successful in ensuring that Emira and Kelley part ways, assuming correctly that Emira would lay the blame of the leaked footage at Kelley’s feet. Alix revels in schadenfreude over the misfortune that Emira feels she has called upon herself (by not deleting the footage altogether, or in failure to judge correctly the character of Kelley) and wades out again in a role of a white protector. She offers Emira the cushion of an all-benefits attached full-time nanny job and also the chance at an interview, a way of clearing the air over any nasty repercussions of the video-leak. Her resentment is of course misdirected, but the novel finds final favour in how it deals the perfect hand to Emira, at the last time of her asking. Through the intervention of her friend Zara, Emira gathers (much to her dismay) that she had completely miscalculated the motives of her preying employer. She learns the truth of who leaked the video and finally takes it on herself to out the truth, once and for all.

While Alix fawns in front of the camera, buttressed in her belief that even while wealthy, she had been “progressive and willing to aid others [...] in need of protection from the greedy masses” (hooks, 2000, p. 74) by arranging the airtime with Emira and her husband’s co-host, Emira superbly deflects the questions of the presenter to assert that she will, after all, not be joining the Chamberlains as a full-time nanny, but rather stick with her administrative role at the Green Party. It is just like Alix to turn vengeful from this instance, unmasking any and all pretence at civility when she charges Emira with breaching the

boundaries of their contract. By choosing to centre her own needs vis-à-vis Emira's refusal to continue their employment relationship, Alix refuels the logic that serves racism and reveals herself to be completely hollow, despite all her posturing as a progressive woman. Her failure to empathize with Emira, coupled with her antagonistic actions, shows how the battle between two white, frangible peoples disproportionately affects the lives of other, less-privileged people, and throws light on the deleterious effects of white classist materialism in the modern-day United States.

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